

Coming to a Screen Near You: The Rubin Observatory Education and Public Outreach Program

Kristen Metzger (NOIRLab/Rubin)

Figure 1: Space Surveyors: an interactive game that simulates operating a survey telescope.
 Credit: J. Pinto (NOIRLab/Rubin)

The Rubin Observatory Education and Public Outreach (EPO) team has begun to roll out a program that invites teens and adults to engage with Rubin Observatory and explore the Universe. Like Rubin Observatory as a whole, the EPO program capitalizes on new technologies and strategies — in this case to reach a whole new audience of science-interested teens and adults who might not already be engaged with, or highly knowledgeable about, astronomy. This focus on reaching a broader audience through a data-driven, interactive EPO program appealed to the US National Science Foundation (NSF), which provided construction funding for Rubin Observatory. In fact, the Rubin EPO program is the first astronomy outreach program to be fully funded by NSF during a project’s construction phase. Having the time and resources to develop this program before the start of the astronomical survey has allowed the EPO team to consider

their audiences and build their program strategically — and they’re excited to share the results!

The first thing to know about the Rubin EPO program is that it’s all online, which means that anyone with an internet connection can access the whole range of materials developed by Rubin’s EPO team. Since more and more people — especially teens and young adults — are using mobile devices to interact with digital content, the Rubin EPO team has designed the materials to be mobile-friendly and easy to navigate from a phone or tablet. The EPO program is also available in English and Spanish, so it will welcome Chilean audiences as well as Spanish speakers in the US and worldwide. Additionally, the EPO team is dedicated to following best practices for Web accessibility and strives to provide an inclusive online experience.

A pillar of the Rubin EPO program is its formal education component, which focuses on engaging advanced middle school to introductory college students with real astronomy data. The program centers around a series of investigations and a full complement of teacher support materials, all designed under the supervision of Education Specialist Ardis Herrold, who taught astronomy in the classroom for more than 35 years. Investigations are engaging and interactive and don't require special software or teachers to download data — a browser is all that's needed. Best of all, they're free! The investigations follow a progression of concepts and tasks that are necessary for students to learn the big ideas of each investigation. All materials have been tested with thousands of students and teachers to help ensure success in the classroom, and the support materials provide teachers with everything they need to easily implement these tools with their students. The EPO team will release two complete investigations initially, and there are several more in the late stages of development, so teachers can expect at least one more in the next few months. The formal education team has also started offering professional development workshops in the US and Chile to introduce teachers to the investigations and connect them with the Rubin Observatory community.

Rubin EPO also offers a range of products for the general public, including a website, animated videos, and an image gallery. While designing these, the EPO team referenced the outcomes of their evaluation effort to research what inspires (and what intimidates) people when it comes to astronomy. The result is that the new website is filled with articles written in an informal, conversational style that uses analogies and real-world examples to make astronomy concepts interesting and relevant. The website includes a section called *Rubin Voices*, which highlights the people who are working to build Rubin Observatory or preparing for the science that Rubin will enable. Each profile includes a short audio clip, so visitors can listen to people expressing their passion for science in their own words. On the website visitors will also find a gallery of visually engaging images and graphics, all available to download and share, as well as animated videos that introduce Rubin Observatory and explain some of Rubin's main science goals.

But how will people who aren't already engaged with astronomy find these

opportunities? Rubin EPO's outreach program uses social media as a primary method to reach new audiences. That's where people — especially young people — are currently getting information and building communities. Rubin Observatory is building a strategic social media presence that focuses not just on sharing information but also on engaging in conversation with followers, capitalizing on trends to stay relevant, and building relationships with other influential people and organizations to expand audience reach. As Stephanie Deppe, the EPO team's Astronomy Content Strategist, explains, "We won't rely on people to find us — we'll go to them!"

A challenge for the EPO team as they transition to an operational state is that the astronomical data from Rubin Observatory, which will drive all the interactive features of the program, aren't available yet. So while some of the team's products are essentially ready to go, they won't be released until they can incorporate real Rubin data, giving users the full experience. Two such examples are the *Skyviewer* and the *Orbitviewer*.

Figure 2: The new public-facing website for Rubin Observatory features engaging visuals, and information about Rubin technology and science, written in an approachable, conversational style
Credit: J. Pinto (NOIRLab/Rubin)

Figure 3: A visual representation of the science themes addressed in the Rubin EPO formal education investigations
 Credit: J. Pinto (NOIRLab/Rubin)

The *Skyviewer* is an all-sky visualization tool that enables users to navigate around the Southern Hemisphere night sky (the observatory is in Chile), as seen by Rubin Observatory, and select featured objects to learn more about them. The EPO team’s user testing campaign revealed that some individuals are much more likely to engage with these types of tools if they have a more guided experience, so that option is available as well. The *Orbitviewer* is another exploratory tool that will offer both a guided and a free-form experience for people to interact with Rubin Observatory’s observations and discoveries in our Solar System. Watch for these tools when Rubin starts producing data!

One other major program component that the EPO team will introduce after data starts flowing facilitates participation in Rubin science by...anyone!

The team has partnered with *Zooniverse*, a prominent citizen-science platform based at Oxford University in the UK, to develop a tool that will make it quick and easy for primary investigators to create projects and populate them with Rubin data. That’s great news for scientists who need the help of lots of human eyes to interpret their data and great news for anyone who wants to contribute to real, cutting-edge astronomy.

So there’s still lots to come, but the Rubin EPO team wants to educate and entertain you in the meantime — so they created a simple, fun, browser-based game called *Space Surveyors*. The game teaches players how a survey telescope works as they attempt to capture images of stars, galaxies, and moving objects in the night sky. The EPO team invites you to visit spacesurveyors.app and try for a high score!